

BioMedData Deliverable D3.5

Establish monitoring of adherence to data management routines at Norwegian life science research infrastructures

Project Title BioMedData - an infrastructure for data sharing and management
Grant Agreement [295932](#)
Work Package Title WP2 Building support for data management in Life Sciences

DOI

Authors [Federico Bianchini](#), Centre for Bioinformatics, University of Oslo; ELIXIR Norway, BioMedData
(arranged by surnames in alphabetical order):

[Korbinian Bösl](#), Computational Biology Unit, University of Bergen; ELIXIR Norway, Centre for Digital Life Norway, BioMedData

[Nazeefa Fatima](#), Centre for Bioinformatics, University of Oslo; ELIXIR Norway, BioMedData

[Katarina Fritz-Wallace](#), Department of Biomedicine, University of Bergen; NAPI, BioMedData

[Xian Hu](#), Norwegian Center for Molecular Medicine, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Oslo; Radiumhoospitalet, Oslo University Hospital; NALMIN, BioMedData

[Torill Eidhammer Sjøbakk](#), Department of Circulation and Medical Imaging, NTNU; Norwegian university of science and technology; NORMOLIM, BioMedData

[Michal Torma](#), Natural History Museum, University of Oslo

Content

About	3
Template	4
1. Project Planning Phase	4
2. Data Collecting Phase	4
3. Data Analysis/Processing Phase	4
4. Archiving Phase	4
5. Future Plans	4
Norwegian Research Infrastructures	5
NALMIN: Norwegian Advanced Light Microscopy Imaging Network	5
Project Planning Phase	5
Data Collecting Phase	5
Archiving Phase	5
Future Plans	6
NORMOLIM: Norwegian Molecular Imaging Infrastructure	7
Project Planning Phase	7
Data Collecting Phase	7
Data Analysis/Processing Phase	7
Archiving Phase	8
Future Plans	8
National network of Advanced Proteomics Infrastructure (NAPI)	9
Project Planning Phase	9
Data Collecting Phase	9
Data Analysis/Processing Phase	9
Archiving Phase	9
Future Plans	10
NorSeq: Norwegian Consortium for Sequencing and Personalized Medicine	11
Project Planning Phase	11
Data Collecting Phase	12
Data Analysis/Processing Phase	12
Archiving Phase	13
Future Plans	14
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Norway	15
Project Planning Phase	15
Data Collecting Phase	15
Data Analysis/Processing Phase	15
Archiving Phase	15
Future Plans	16

About

Research Infrastructures (RIs) play a critical role in facilitating scientific advancements through the provision of specialised services, resources, and technologies. Regularly monitoring outputs that are a direct result of these services, such as sample depositions to repositories, publications generated from projects, and other data management routines are important for a multitude of reasons. First, it ensures data quality and integrity; regular monitoring helps in identifying potential discrepancies in the data, thereby enhancing its precision and reliability. Secondly, it assists in evaluating the performance and productivity of the facilities; tracking allows to collect key metrics that in result helps to assess impact of data management services provided by the infrastructures. Monitoring data management routines also aids in demonstrating accountability and transparency, which allows to gain trust from existing and potential stakeholders including funding bodies. In this report, we focus on monitoring of data management routines at Norwegian RIs and their core facilities and highlight strengths and weaknesses, in the context of the life sciences ecosystem and the adoption of metadata.

Metadata adoption is crucial for ensuring interoperability and reusability of datasets, which are central to the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). However, the onus for creating, collecting and managing metadata is usually on researchers/users that may lack the necessary support and knowledge. This can lead to inconsistencies and reduced data quality, making monitoring more critical to maintain data integrity.

We highlight the importance of ELIXIR's deposition databases that facilitate API-based monitoring, which can streamline the process of tracking data submissions and usage across multiple platforms. We showcase how this can work in practice (see sections on NAPI and NorSeq, pages 10-15). However, it is worth noting that the lack of a specific repository or centralised system for endpoint monitoring can be a hindrance - without such a system, it's challenging to provide comprehensive oversight and ensure compliance with standards.

In addition to tracking data and metadata, we believe the implementation of a national strategy is necessary to uniquely identify and connect projects, institutions, funders, and researchers. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for publications and datasets, enable tracking of research outcomes with a higher accuracy. However, some domain-specific repositories currently lack PID support, which hampers the ability to effectively monitor the dissemination and impact of research. Similarly, there is currently no consistent national use of PIDs for researchers (e.g. ORCIDs) and institutions (e.g. Research Organisation Registries (RORs)) for data deposition.

To address these challenges, we believe there is a need for systematic efforts to enhance metadata quality and to incorporate PIDs into all facets of the research data lifecycle. This would entail educating and providing resources to RI users, considering and establishing suitable toolkits and standards for monitoring and reporting, and developing policies that mandate adherence to these practices. Properly addressing these elements will significantly improve services as well as the transparency and quality of data generated and processed at the RIs, ultimately contributing to the progress of Norwegian life science research data management.

Template

We provide here a template that is categorised into four sections, and a collection of questions/considerations that help address strengths, weaknesses, and potential improvements for each category in a context of life sciences data management.

1. Project Planning Phase

1. Describe how you interact with users before they start the project.
 - a. Are the users made aware of the requirements e.g. around standardisation and metadata recording?
 - b. Are the users advised where to submit their data and encouraged to collect all the information regarding this step at an early stage?
2. Describe how you interact with users for RDM planning.
 - a. Is a Data Management Plan (DMP) requested by your RI from the user?
 - b. How is the DMP shared with the infrastructure?
 - c. Does the RI provide feedback on the DMP?
 - d. Is the DMP compliant with the machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) standard as recommended by the Research Council of Norway? How is this verified/validated?
 - e. Is any information automatically transferred from the DMP to the management system of choice of the infrastructure?
 - f. Describe how the RDM of a project (for aspects controlled by the RI) are documented (data and metadata) and supervised.

2. Data Collecting Phase

1. Describe your quality control routine (e.g. data integrity, quality measures, but also completeness of metadata).
2. How does your RI determine which metadata standards to use?
 - a. Are metadata standards uniform across the RI nodes?
 - b. Is the adherence of such standards for deposition to a domain repository assessed?
 - c. In which forms are these standards shared with the users?
 - d. Are there monitoring routines for the completeness of the metadata forms?
3. Do you track/document data backups for users and the transfer to users?

3. Data Analysis/Processing Phase

1. How does the RI track software versions (e.g. for data processing and quality control) of tools used at the RI?
2. How does the RI ensure the reproducibility of the workflow?

4. Archiving Phase

1. What is your RI's internal routine for post-archiving? Is there a system in place to monitor the upload to repositories of data produced by the RI? How is this data labelled as being produced by the RI? Is the information on the uploaded datasets linked to publications?
2. If you have a dashboard, put a Zenodo link to the code and include a plot.

5. Future Plans

What would be the ideal solution to fill the gaps in your monitoring routine?

Norwegian Research Infrastructures

NALMIN: Norwegian Advanced Light Microscopy Imaging Network

RI PAL: Xian Hu (Edna)

Contact: xianh@uio.no, nalmin.no

Project Planning Phase

The vision of the Norwegian Advanced Light Microscopy Imaging Network (NALMIN) is to offer Norwegian researchers access to state-of-the-art light microscopy technology for imaging biologically and biomedically significant molecules at resolutions ranging from high to ultra-high, across various systems including microorganisms, cell cultures, plants, and small animals. We advise our users to carefully consider and plan for image data management prior to commencing their imaging experiments on our platforms. Common resources that we typically recommend to our users include the RDMkit page on Bioimaging Data https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/bioimaging_data, and Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) instance by ELIXIR Norway <https://elixir-no.ds-wizard.org/wizard/>.

Data Collecting Phase

During the data collection phase, users typically store their data on short-term storage media provided by individual nodes or within their own research environment. This data remains in "hot storage" for a few months while undergoing processing and curation, after which it is transferred to long-term storage (cold storage). During this transition, we encourage users to ensure the accuracy of metadata and maintain oversight of the data processing pipeline.

Optical microscopes offer various imaging modalities, each potentially associated with different metadata. While most of our equipment stores metadata alongside raw images, not all do so uniformly. Our primary responsibility during this phase is to ensure that platform users are aware of this variability and to double-check their metadata to comply with existing standards, such as REMBI. Additionally, we remind users to maintain a reproducible data processing pipeline to facilitate future analyses.

Archiving Phase

After processing and obtaining the primary data required for their research project, users typically transfer the data from short-term "hot storage" to long-term "cold storage." While we are in the process of developing a common image storage governed by an OMERO server (part of Open Microscopy Environment (OME)) for the long term, many users currently utilise their own methods for long-term storage.

Our primary responsibility at this stage is to assist users in preparing their data for long-term storage. We typically advise users to either adopt a common nomenclature (syntax) based on existing community standards or establish and document a system within their own research group. Additionally, we recommend that users convert raw data into a

non-proprietary format at this stage. If this is not feasible, we suggest performing a backup of the existing software version to ensure future accessibility.

Future Plans

We are currently in the process of developing an OMERO image data storage server, which will provide our users with the option to store their data with the core facility. As part of our user introduction program, we will integrate knowledge of data management, emphasising the FAIR principles. Furthermore, we are committed to supporting our users in storing and sharing their data in a manner that is FAIR-compatible, ensuring that their research outputs are maximally accessible and usable within the scientific community.

NORMOLIM: Norwegian Molecular Imaging Infrastructure

RI PAL: Torill E. Sjøbakk

Contact: torill.sjobakk@ntnu.no

Project Planning Phase

NORMOLIM is open for applicants with biomedical or medical research projects. Before applying for access, NORMOLIM strongly encourages the applicants to contact one of the three sites in the infrastructure directly to discuss the feasibility and utility of the applicant's project. The NORMOLIM staff will contribute with their competence in the planning of studies and development of protocols, procedures, experimental design, choice and optimization of image acquisition, and analysis. To ensure compliance with Norwegian laws and regulations, the staff will also monitor and aid during all use of animals in the preclinical studies.

For Data Management Planning (DMP) the current policy for the infrastructure (<https://normolim.w.uib.no/files/2018/11/NORMOLIM-Access-and-Data-Management-Policy-1.pdf>) recommends the checklist from the Digital Curation Centre (<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans/checklist>). For future projects, NORMOLIM will recommend the DMP exemplar for Preclinical imaging at the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) instance by ELIXIR Norway (<https://elixir-no.ds-wizard.org/wizard/>). The infrastructure also recommends the users to explore the research management guidance at the RDMkit (<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>) and also encourages users to explore the library guidance for data management at each university/institution.

The users own the data produced in their project using the facilities at the infrastructure, and therefore it is users that are responsible for making their data as FAIR as possible.

Data Collecting Phase

At the three sites in NORMOLIM, raw imaging and spectroscopic data with metadata attached to each image or spectrum are produced. The data created are named and stored according to guidelines for each instrument at the facilities. File names include acquisition date, username, patient/sample identifier, experiment number, treatment conditions, and groups. The structure of this may differ within the three sites since each facility consists of different instruments and corresponding analyses. The infrastructure users must complete the essential metadata for their own data set produced. Currently, there are no monitoring routines for the completeness of metadata forms.

Data Analysis/Processing Phase

To ensure reproducible results, regular quality checks are required and run for all instruments at the facilities. Data are stored as securely as possible on dedicated servers operated by the institutional IT departments. No regular backup is taken since the users are responsible for their data after using the instruments. Data sharing happens on request with the owner's permission. There is no track of software versions.

Archiving Phase

The users own the data and are ultimately responsible for making their data as FAIR as possible. The facility has an advising and educational role towards the users. Data repositories that can enable sharing and reuse of the data according to the FAIR principles are missing. Datasets are linked to publications according to the requests by the journals. A system to monitor any upload of data to repositories is missing.

Future Plans

An ideal solution to fill the gaps in the RI monitoring routine would be having a public repository of metadata information for preclinical image datasets from any imaging modality associated with peer-reviewed publications, where the metadata information is organised in a proper schema to create a standard metadata model for preclinical imaging so that an endpoint monitoring would become possible.

National network of Advanced Proteomics Infrastructure (NAPI)

RI PAL: Katarina Fritz-Wallace

Contact: katarina.fritz-wallace@uib.no
<https://www.napi.uio.no/>

Project Planning Phase

Across NAPI nodes, metadata collection is handled differently due to different software availability and restrictions in IT infrastructure.

At the NAPI node at UiB, Bookitlab is being used for sample submission and metadata can be submitted during sample request. Depending on the user and project the integrity of the metadata varies.

The sample request will be used to ask users for a data management plan and give guidelines on where to find help. In practice, we see that very few users have a data management plan, especially for smaller parts of projects where a DMP is considered omittable.

Data Collecting Phase

There are currently no metadata standards uniformly adopted across NAPI nodes. The proteomics community has adopted “Minimum information about a Proteomics Experiment” (MIAPE)¹ and data submitted to public repositories such as PRIDE has to fulfill those standards. However these are not required at NAPI when samples are submitted.

Metadata that is collected is needed for sample preparation and data analysis through the RI. Beyond that, a user is responsible for the collection of metadata.

Data Analysis/Processing Phase

Reproducibility of workflows is ensured through regular running of quality control samples and analysis with standardized workflows. This process varies across the nodes of NAPI, due to different analysis instruments as well as data analysis software.

Archiving Phase

A monitoring tool was established that tracks the submissions of Norwegian research groups to the Proteomics Identifications Database (PRIDE) - see figure 1. The code is open-source and it is available on GitHub² and it is identified with Zenodo³. This monitoring tool assumes that datasets from a research group submitted to PRIDE were analyzed/processed at the NAPI node of the same institution. However, there are a few pitfalls with this assumption, such as 1) projects are not always analysed at the same university, sometimes samples are even sent abroad, and 2) some journals require the

¹ <https://www.psidev.info/miape>

² <https://github.com/KatarinaFritz/EBI-db-app/blob/master/app.R>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10876293>

repository of the dataset in a different database than PRIDE, thus these datasets will not show up.

Users should be advised to submit their data to public repositories. However, data is usually only submitted when journals require submission. Datasets not used for publication will mostly never be submitted.

Choose input below

Figure 1. Entries uploaded to PRIDE database from NAPI partners. The image displays a dashboard with a drop-down menu on left and stacked bar plot on right. The purpose is to monitor submissions to the PRIDE database; the plot here shows entries from the period 2019-2023. UiO has been the main submitter followed by UiB and NMBU.

Future Plans

Ideally, there should be a uniform sample submission tool across the RI nodes, which collects metadata and tracks submission to public repositories. As this seems to be challenging, the plan is to at least coordinate the necessary information needed by users, increase awareness of FAIR data handling and support submission to public repositories. Tracking the submissions of the different NAPI nodes could be achieved by collecting accession numbers/data set IDs or the use of a common NAPI brokering account.

In general, users should be made aware of the necessity of having DMP and FAIR data management principles.

Lastly, we are trying to implement safe data handling for sensitive data. Even without patient information the analysis results of human samples might sooner or later be considered as sensitive information and need to be handled accordingly.

NorSeq: Norwegian Consortium for Sequencing and Personalized Medicine

RI PAL: Nazeefa Fatima, Federico Bianchini

Contact: nazeefaf@uio.no, fredebi@uio.no

Project Planning Phase

NorSeq assists users to help decide a relevant sequencing strategy for a project and has, therefore, developed a Project Request Form⁴ to get an overview of a project. The form allows a user to indicate information such as the sample type, the sequencing platform, read length and type. There is, similarly, a web version of the form⁵ collecting similar information in a more structured way. When an experiment design has been agreed upon, the users are invited to fill in a more detailed online submission form⁶ and two additional documents to capture the information regarding the samples, the sample submission form⁷ (for Illumina samples) and table⁸. Note, that sample submissions for PacBio (long-read) sequencing require a dedicated form⁹.

Whilst a good portion of the metadata suitable for submission to domain repositories is collected as part of the process, the information is currently not transferred into specific formats e.g. the sample checklists¹⁰ provided by the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). This hinders data submission to domain-specific repositories and can be addressed by mapping between the current documentation requested and the checklist. As part of the activity of this project, we are pointing the users to the most suitable checklists based on the information about the samples. This is currently being implemented as a dedicated section in the online submission form. In this way, NorSeq users are advised both on where to submit their data and on the standardised form of the metadata required for such a submission.

NorSeq is still at an early stage in the process of verifying the validity and monitoring Data Management Plans (DMPs) for each user's project. At the current stage, DMPs are not strictly required for initiating a project however NorSeq users are recommended to have a DMP. Moreover, users' DMPs are currently not shared with the infrastructure and therefore no feedback is provided. We recommend our users to use ELIXIR Norway's instance of the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW)¹¹ and pre-filled DMP templates for non-quantitative sequencing (which is developing as part of BioMedData) - the templates can be found in drop-down under Project Templates in ELIXIR-Norway's DSW. In addition, we point users to other informative resources such as ELIXIR's RDMkit¹² and BioMedData's Life Science Research Data Management Lookup¹³ and, in particular, to its "cheat sheet" on best practices for sequencing data¹⁴. We will be establishing routines around DMPs as their use in the life sciences will become more extensive. If NorSeq users opt to have their data

⁴ <https://www.sequencing.uio.no/forms/project-request-form.docx>

⁵ https://www.sequencing.uio.no/forms/projectrequest_v2.html

⁶ <https://nettskjema.no/a/nsc-project#/page/1>

⁷ [https://www.sequencing.uio.no/forms/sample-submission-form-\(illumina\).docx](https://www.sequencing.uio.no/forms/sample-submission-form-(illumina).docx)

⁸ https://www.sequencing.uio.no/forms/sample_table_96_template.xlsx

⁹ https://www.sequencing.uio.no/pacbio-submission/pacbio_sample-delivery-form_2024.xlsx

¹⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

¹¹ <https://elixir-no.ds-wizard.org/wizard/>

¹² <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

¹³ <https://elixir.no/rdm-lookup/>

¹⁴ <https://elixir.no/rdm-lookup/sequencing>

delivered to the ELIXIR-operated Norwegian e-Infrastructure for the Life Sciences (NeLS)¹⁵, they can create a user's account and quota from a machine-actionable DMP (maDMP).

Data Collecting Phase

Metadata that is collected involves information on a library kit used for an experiment, what software version was used on the sequencer and what software was used for demultiplexing. Metadata collection is done for quality control. This information is stored in a structured format. Not all metadata, however, is exposed to the users as it may not be relevant to them. One example of this is Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) metadata. FASTQC and MultiQC analyses are performed as a quality control step, although quality control reports are not always required by every user.

The various nodes of NorSeq define their own metadata requirements based on information for carrying out the experiments. These are not metadata "standards", as there is no formal agreement in NorSeq about their formalisation. They are, moreover, not mapped to international community standards (e.g. Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence¹⁶) or checklists from repositories such as ENA. The metadata are mainly collected using the sample spreadsheet. There is currently no monitoring for the completeness of the metadata forms.

Data transfers are done using the NeLS system. In terms of long-read sequencing data, delivery is often done using FileSender. For large data (e.g. 1 TB), reads and analysis results are uploaded to a server with a password-protected delivery. Data backups are currently tracked using a Library Information Management System (LIMS) otherwise Excel spreadsheets.

Data Analysis/Processing Phase

It is often end-users that perform analysis and processing of sequenced data e.g. a bioinformatician in a team carries out sequence alignment, assembly, post-alignment filtering, variant calling, annotation, and data visualisation. Although the amount of projects registered for sequencing vary, 10-20% of projects require support from NorSeq for bioinformatics analysis, and such bioinformatics services serve mostly as external collaboration. NorSeq offers a number of bioinformatics services¹⁷ and makes sure to provide key metadata such as tool/software versions for both quality control and data processing.

NorSeq also offers various data delivery services provided by other entities. These services include NeLS from ELIXIR Norway¹⁸, the National Infrastructure for Research Data (NIRD)¹⁹ from Sigma2 and, in the case of human or otherwise sensitive data, the Norwegian Trusted Research Environment, i.e. the Services for Sensitive Data (TSD)²⁰ in Oslo, SAFE²¹ in Bergen and HUNT Cloud²² in Trondheim. In these cases, it is not NorSeq's responsibility

¹⁵ <https://nels.bioinfo.no/>

¹⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.9aa0zp>

¹⁷ <https://www.sequencing.uio.no/illumina-services/8.%20Bioinformatic%20services/>

¹⁸ https://elixir.no/Services-bak/data_produced_NorSeq

¹⁹ https://documentation.sigma2.no/files_storage/nird_lmd.html

²⁰ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/index.html>

²¹ <https://www.uib.no/en/foremployees/131011/safe>

²² <https://www.ntnu.edu/mh/huntcloud>

to monitor any process beyond data delivery. For the reproducibility of workflow pipelines, software such as Nextflow, Snakemake and Singularity are used.

Archiving Phase

As the users are the data owners, it is not the responsibility of the RI to archive the data. As part of BioMedData, a script for monitoring uploads to repositories including the aforementioned ENA and the Sequence Read Archive (SRA)²³ has been created. This script is available as a Zenodo release²⁴. In this script, we make use of EBI search²⁵ and, in particular, of its REST Application Programming Interface (API) to monitor the uploads of samples related to sequencing experiments. We use the *sra-samples* endpoint, which provides information on data uploaded both to ENA and SRA.

When using this approach, some challenges arise: firstly, the field indicating the country indicates the country of origin of the sample, not the country that generated the sequencing data. This implies that all the institutions from other countries sequencing samples of Norwegian origin are included in the query and need to be filtered out. On top of this, there is no indicator of whether the data was produced by any of the NorSeq nodes. One could assume that a large chunk of the sequencing data produced in Norway originated at a NorSeq node, but there is no way of demonstrating this formally. We have, thus, opted to include only results linked to Norwegian universities with a focus on the ones where a NorSeq node is present (Bergen, Oslo, Trondheim and Tromsø) and The Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU). We have also included data from the National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), one of the major contributors to the bulk of Norwegian sample data on ENA. When considering these institutions, filtering is not straightforward, as the metadata structure from the EBI search does not offer controlled vocabularies for sequencing centres nor supports identifiers from The Research Organisation Registry (ROR)²⁶. As it is evident from the code, we manually selected all the centres' names that were compatible with one of the institutions mentioned above. On top of this being prone to human error and increasing significantly the amount of work required to complete this task, this might cause issues in the future if data is uploaded using other different names for the centres. We believe it is up to the EBI search service to improve the standardisation of these metadata.

The results of this analysis are presented in the plots below (Figure 2). No significant amount of submissions occurred before 2016. While NTNU was a prime mover in submission to ENA and maintained over time a steady amount of submissions, UiO is responsible for the largest chunk of submissions from universities from 2018, although the amount of submissions per year is not steady. The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (also known as FHI, Folkehelseinstituttet) started submitting data with a 2-year delay when compared to universities but reached a comparable amount of submission by 2019 and, most notably, submitted a massive amount of data in 2022. This is a key result both for FHI and for ELIXIR Norway, the official broker (i.e. submitter) of FHI data to ENA²⁷.

²³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>

²⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/10948339>

²⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ebisearch/about>

²⁶ <https://ror.org/>

²⁷ <https://elixir.no/news/52/63/ELIXIR-Norway-broker-data-to-ENA>

Figure 2: Genomic Samples Submitted to ENA/SRA. Number of samples submitted to INSDC databases every year per Norwegian institution including the National Institute of Public Health (NIPH/FHI), from the period of 2016-2023.

Future Plans

Future plans involve ensuring that there is successful alignment across all NorSeq nodes in terms of data management. The way to achieve this is by taking small steps such as monitoring of sample submissions (as shown in Figure 2) implemented in a dashboard that can be maintained over a long-term period. This could be coupled with tracking of research publications associated with submitted datasets. Currently, NorSeq keeps an account of publications associated with core facility sequencing data through tracking acknowledgement of NorSeq in user's publications. Similar to other RIs, NorSeq also aims to raise awareness among users on having a DMP in place and this will be done by mentioning DMP templates in the sample submission form as well as in the standard email sent to users when a project is registered. In the future, the goal is to make it a policy that DMP is a requirement for a project to be accepted.

Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Norway

RI PAL: Michal Torma

Contact: michato@uio.no

Project Planning Phase

At GBIF Norway, the initiation of our monitoring processes occurs through direct communication with data publishers, primarily via our dedicated support channel at helpdesk@gbif.no. Upon receipt of a query or request for assistance, a designated staff member is assigned to the task, leading to the creation of a tracking issue within our GitHub repository (accessible at [GBIF Norway Helpdesk Issues](#)). This stage is critical for the systematic collection of datasets' metadata, which adheres to the Ecological Metadata Language (EML) standard, as part of the Darwin Core (DwC) archive publication process.

Data Collecting Phase

The approach to dataset publication is tailored to the unique characteristics of each dataset. For bespoke datasets developed by researchers for specific projects, the initial step involves publication on Zenodo in their original form. Subsequently, custom Python scripts are developed to restructure the dataset into a DwC-compatible format for publication via one of our Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT) instances. In cases where datasets are subject to regular updates, GBIF Norway devises custom automated solutions that are compatible with the publisher's technological infrastructure. The IPT platform serves a dual role, facilitating both the publication of individual dataset versions and their backup. This infrastructure is supported by our private Kubernetes (K8S) cluster hosted on DigitalOcean, with additional data storage and offsite backup provided through the Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data (NIRD).

Data Analysis/Processing Phase

During the Data Analysis and Processing Phase at GBIF Norway, our primary focus is on the essential processing required to standardise datasets in preparation for their publication. This phase involves a meticulous examination and manipulation of data to ensure it conforms to the Darwin Core (DwC) standards, which is crucial for seamless integration into the GBIF network. Our processing tasks are streamlined and do not typically extend into elaborate data analysis. However, for the purpose of deriving advanced statistics and insights into our dataset contributions and overall progress, we leverage GBIF's internal analytics tools and the comprehensive capabilities of Google's BigQuery. By utilising these resources, we can perform in-depth analyses, extracting valuable information about dataset characteristics, usage, and trends, which informs our strategic planning and helps us identify areas for improvement and growth.

Archiving Phase

The archival of data mapped to DwC terms for the purposes of indexing and referencing is managed externally by GBIF.org, thus relieving GBIF Norway of the need for additional archiving efforts. An overview of our activities, including detailed reports, is available at [GBIF Norway Country Report](#). To ensure the integrity of dataset ingestion, GBIF

Norway employs daily checks through the IPT Integrity Inspector (details available at [IPT Integrity Inspector GitHub](#)). This proactive monitoring allows for the immediate identification and resolution of ingestion-related issues.

Figure 3: Species occurrence records for the period of 2008-2024. Area plot showing a number of species occurrences in millions with blue and green area denoting animal and plant kingdoms, respectively whereas Other represents fungi, protozoa, bacteria, virus, archaea, and chromista (with highest number of records from fungi). There have been over 800 thousand entry records that are uploaded and published by Norwegian institutions. Information source is the [GBIF Country Report for Norway](#) and the code for data is available on GitHub <https://github.com/gbif-norway/ipt-integrity-inspector>

Future Plans

Looking ahead, GBIF Norway is actively exploring innovative strategies to enhance our data management and publication processes. A key area of focus is the simplification of partial dataset updates, or appends, which will enable data publishers to efficiently update their datasets without the need for complete re-publication. This initiative aims to reduce the operational overhead for both publishers and our infrastructure, making the data update process more agile and responsive to new findings or corrections. Furthermore, we are investigating the potential for annotating individual records within datasets, which would significantly enrich the metadata and improve the quality and utility of the data shared through our platform. Another crucial aspect of our future plans involves the development of robust methods for resolving unique identifiers for individual records. This enhancement will improve data traceability, integrity, and the ability to link datasets across different platforms and studies, fostering greater collaboration and knowledge exchange within the scientific community. Through these strategic initiatives, GBIF Norway is committed to advancing biodiversity data sharing and utilisation, ensuring our infrastructure remains at the forefront of global efforts to understand and preserve our natural world.